

Supplementary Table S2. Purified porcine small intestinal mucin monosaccharide and sialic acid analysis determined by High-Performance Anion-Exchange Chromatography coupled with Pulsed Amperometric Detection (HPAEC-PAD). (GlycoAnalytics).

Monosaccharide	Amount (nmole/5μg of sample)
Fucose	0.17
Galactosamine	0.14
Glucosamine	0.14
Galactose	0.17
Glucose	0.01
Mannose	0.02

Sialic Acid	Amount (pmole/2μg of sample)
Neu5Ac	8.54
Neu5Gc	6.90